

1 **Promoting Human Behaviour Change in a First Opinion**
2 **Veterinary Clinic to improve Home Oral Hygiene in Pets**
3 **Utilising the 5A Consult Model**

4 Lowri Elis-Williams^a (email: leliski@exseed.ed.ac.uk)

5 Fiona McDowall^b (email: Fiona.McDowall@ed.ac.uk)

6 Claire Harrison^a (email: c.harrison@ed.ac.uk)

7 Kirsty Hughes^b (OrcID 0000-0002-2805-4866, email: kirsty.hughes@ed.ac.uk)

8 Arlene Crawford^a (email: arlene.crawford@ed.ac.uk)

9 Jill R D MacKay^{b, c, d} (OrcID 0000-0001-7134-4829, email: jill.mackay@ed.ac.uk)

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11 ^a Hospital for Small Animals, Royal (Dick) School of Veterinary Studies. University of Edinburgh,
12 Easter Bush, Midlothian, EH25 9RG

13 ^b Veterinary Medical Education Division, Royal (Dick) School of Veterinary Studies, University of
14 Edinburgh, Easter Bush, Midlothian, EH25 9RG

15 ^c Animal Welfare Centre, Royal (Dick) School of Veterinary Studies, University of Edinburgh,
16 Easter Bush, Midlothian, EH25 9RG

17 ^d Contact Author: jill.mackay@ed.ac.uk

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19 Abstract

20 The welfare of companion animals is predicated by caregiver management and decision
21 making, and so the veterinary consult is a key intervention point to improve animal welfare. As
22 with many health-related behaviours, instigating long-term changes is a challenge in the
23 veterinary profession, with knowledge-deficit models of human behaviour change proving
24 ineffective at promoting positive welfare for companion animals. Dental care is one of the most
25 prevalent health disorders in the UK, with many pets receiving suboptimal Home Oral Hygiene
26 (HOH) care. This study implemented a Dental Care clinic in the Royal (Dick) School of Veterinary
27 Studies Small Animal General Practice and recruited 61 caregivers to a retention based study
28 looking at changes to HOH. The Dental Clinic followed the 5As consult model, adapted for
29 veterinary use, to promote clinically relevant HOH behavioural changes. Caregivers were
30 surveyed prior to the clinic consult, after the final follow-up consult, and at a six month
31 retention date to explore their HOH. Retention was a challenge in the project, with only 39
32 caregivers attending the clinic, 21 (54%) responding to the End of Clinic survey and 13 (33%)
33 responding to the six month post survey. HOH methods were rated on a 9 point scale, and in
34 the End of Clinic Survey, HOH score had improved by 2.62 points ($t_{\text{student}} = 2.77, p = .01, g_{\text{Hedges}}$
35 $= 0.58, 95\% \text{ CI}[0.13, 1.02]$), however, the study was underpowered to detect significance at the
36 Retention stage ($F_{\text{Fisher}}(1.64, 19.63) = 3.28, p = .07, \omega^2_p = 0.08, 95\% \text{ CI}[0.00, 1.00]$). We discuss
37 the applicability of the 5As model in veterinary behaviour change, and implications for practice.

38

39 Introduction

40 Companion animals are an animal population which are heavily reliant on their caregivers to
41 make informed decisions regarding their health and wellbeing (1). It can be difficult to get
42 direct indications of the companion animal population size, but companion animals represent a
43 large and relatively long-lived animal population. The UK companion dog population was
44 estimated to be between 8.54-15.16 million animals in 2019 (2) with the average UK dog in that
45 period living between 11.19-11.27 years (3), whereas there were an estimated 10.8 million cats
46 in the UK households in 2021(4), with cats considered 'mature' at 7-10 years and geriatric from
47 15 years (5). Since 2010, more US households have a dog than a child (6), with many caregivers
48 internationally considering companion animals to be part of the family, and indeed, childlike to
49 them (7,8). Companion animal management is therefore as varied as individual families can be,
50 in contrast to other large managed animal populations such as production animals, which are
51 often regulated and standardized by food safety legislation and welfare standards (9).

52 Health is a fundamental component of animal welfare, influencing affective state and behaviour
53 (10), and has an important impact on the wellbeing of companion animals. Periodontal disease
54 is a progressive condition which has significant impact on the welfare of the animal (11–13),
55 and affect a range of companion animals from dogs (14), cats (15), and rabbits (16). Periodontal
56 disease is one of the most common conditions affecting cats and dogs in the UK (14). It has a
57 complex pathology which is initiated by oral bacteria found in the plaque matrix which
58 accumulates on the crown of the tooth (supragingival). The plaque extends under the gingival
59 sulcus (subgingival) where the bacteria causes inflammation of the gingiva (gingivitis) and leads

60 to periodontitis (inflammation and destruction of the periodontium, the supporting structures
61 around the tooth). Periodontitis results in pain, infection, alveolar bone loss and eventual tooth
62 loss if left untreated (13). Periodontitis is irreversible once established with treatment options
63 including periodontal surgery to promote reattachment of the periodontium or, more
64 commonly, extraction of affected teeth. As such, removing plaque is an extremely important
65 preventative and therapeutic treatment for early periodontal disease (gingivitis). There are a
66 range of methods that caregivers can use to achieve this, and support their companion animal's
67 periodontal health, including manual removal through brushing and certain food or chews, and
68 the provision of active ingredients in paste, food, or water (17). Despite this relatively simple
69 recommendation, periodontal disease remains highly prevalent in companion animal
70 populations (14,18,19), suggesting that Home Oral Hygiene (HOH) management remains
71 suboptimal in these populations. Plaque will build up within 24 hours of brushing, therefore
72 HOH must be performed daily (13).

73

74 A reasonable 'goal' for companion animal welfare would be to support caregivers to achieve
75 better HOH practice, thus reducing periodontal disease in the companion animal population.
76 Indeed, research has suggested that raising awareness of breed impacts on periodontal disease
77 might improve welfare (14). Despite an increasing evidence base for good welfare in companion
78 animals, this high quality evidence has not translated to better management practices (20,21).
79 The theory that caregivers are simply unaware of what needs to be done is known as the
80 Knowledge Deficit Model in human behaviour change, with the assumption that a change in
81 knowledge will promote a change in attitude which will change practice (22). This approach has

82 been demonstrated as largely ineffective in animal welfare (23,24), and reflects an ongoing lack
83 of underpinning human behavioural change theory in the promotion of animal welfare
84 interventions (25). To support animal welfare, interventions must incorporate human
85 behavioural change theories which recognise the complexity and uniqueness of animal
86 management, particularly in companion animal management (26,27).

87

88 One human behavioural change model which has seen limited veterinary application, but has
89 been shown effective in a range of human clinical settings is the 5As model (26). The 5As model
90 is not a model intended for research, but was developed in tobacco addiction treatment as a
91 clinical approach to changing behaviours (28). The model inherently reflects the uniqueness of
92 each setting and ensures that individual needs and barriers are centred in any treatment plan
93 (29,30). While the model was initially developed to promote the cessation of a behaviour
94 (smoking tobacco) it has been used in settings to promote other health conscious behaviours,
95 such as healthy practices for weight loss (31). It has also been utilised in paediatric settings for
96 weight loss incorporating caregiver interactions with patient behaviours (32,33). In this study,
97 we explored the utility of the 5As model in veterinary practice with a view to supporting HOH
98 practices. We instituted a Dental Clinic with a consult plan based on the 5As model, and
99 recruited participants to evaluate long term behavioural changes related to HOH following the
100 clinic consults. To our knowledge, this is the first research study exploring the 5As model in the
101 veterinary context.

102

103 We hypothesised that:

104 H¹₀: Caregiver knowledge regarding Home Oral Hygiene method effectiveness would not
105 change following the dental clinic

106 H²₀: The caregiver self-reported frequency of effective Home Oral Hygiene behaviours
107 would not change following the dental clinic

108 H³₀: Overall caregiver Home Oral Hygiene behaviour would not improve following the
109 dental clinic.

110

111 **Methods**

112 **Ethics and Availability**

113 This project was granted ethical approval by the Royal (Dick) School of Veterinary Studies
114 Human Ethics Review Committee (Reference: HERC_2024_005).

115 Data and code for analyses are hosted on the Open Science Framework
116 (https://osf.io/x5mdy/?view_only=e4bb8786633d4c4d9252bc354c8165b1, anonymised for
117 peer review)

118

119 **Researcher Position Statement**

120 Ideological biases permeate and influence researcher behaviour even when researchers profess
121 highly positivist and empirical theoretical stances (34), so we follow 2025 issued
122 recommendations (35) to consider what personal experiences and characteristics are likely to
123 impact the presentation and analysis of data. JRDM was the lead on study design and analysis,
124 and is not a veterinary professional, but has worked in animal and childcare settings for a
125 number of years. She describes herself as principally a methodologist working in veterinary
126 education and animal welfare, with a socio-constructivist epistemological position. LEW is
127 general practice veterinary surgeon with an academic interest and teaching roles in Veterinary
128 Communication, CH is a registered veterinary nurse with a Veterinary Technician Specialty in Dentistry
129 and a background in clinical veterinary nursing and veterinary dentistry education, FM is a registered
130 veterinary nurse with an oncology speciality and a lecturer in veterinary education with a

131 background in psychology and communication and KH is a veterinarian and researcher in
132 veterinary education. Additionally, we have made a number of conscious decisions in our
133 language, referring to animal caregivers due to ongoing concerns with the ethics of business in
134 veterinary care (36,37), and referring to animals as he/she/they instead of 'it' (38).

135

136 **Study Design**

137 This study was divided into four distinct phases: Recruitment, Initial Consult, Follow-Up
138 Consult(s), and Retention. We utilised the 5As Model of Behavioural Change (28) within the
139 Dental Clinic to identify and promote enduring behavioural change with relation to Home Oral
140 Hygiene behaviours. A series of three surveys, in the Recruitment, End of Clinic and Retention
141 phases assessed the caregiver's knowledge, HOH behaviour frequency, and satisfaction with
142 the clinic.

143 **Adapting the 5As Model for Veterinary Use**

144 The 5As strategy for treating tobacco use and dependence (28) was minimally modified to allow
145 for the change in use in promoting effective HOH behaviours (Table 1). There were additionally
146 some minor changes to structure, e.g. the recommendation in the 5A's method to provide
147 social support could not be fulfilled because there are fewer resources to support pet owners
148 with HOH than resources for ceasing tobacco use (in humans). Existing resources were used
149 (39,40) and a separate resource document (see supplementary material Appendix A) was
150 created by the authors.

151 **Table 1:** Modifications to Fiore et al (2000) 5As Model for Dental Veterinary Clinic

152

5A steps	Fiore et al	Veterinary Dental Clinic	Reasoning for change/notes
Ask	Implement an office-wide system that ensures that, for every patient at every clinic visit, tobacco-use status is queried and documented.	Ask what HOH is being used daily at clinic	There was no scope for a practice wide change in this study. <i>Note – assessing the patient’s oral health is done as standard at every annual health check</i>
Advise	In a clear, strong, and personalized manner, urge every tobacco user to quit.	Gave clear, strong, personalised recommendation to start/improve Oral Hygiene. Include examples and advice will be tailored to patient and family	Change from cessation of behaviour to initiating a new behaviour
Assess	Ask every tobacco user if he/she is willing to make a quit attempt at this time (eg, within the next 30 days).	Ask if caregiver willing to start/increase Home Oral Hygiene?	Change from cessation of behaviour to starting a new behaviour
Assist	Help the patient with a quit plan. Provide practical counseling (problem solving/skills training)	Agree on patient and caregiver centered plan with the caregiver Provide a demonstration of how to use products. Discuss potential challenges and offer solutions	Contextualised care for patient and caregiver, rather than patient centered due to veterinary setting

Provide intratreatment social Support.

Help patient obtain extratreatment social support

No social support was offered

The authors are not aware of any current social support and creating social support network is beyond the scope of this study.

Recommend the use of approved pharmacotherapy except in special circumstances.

Provide supplementary materials.

Provide print out/email dental advice handout. Highlight relevant aspects. Include product recommendations

A caregiver information sheet out was created by the authors explaining each HOH method and advice on using it. (Appendix A)

A list of VOHC approved products available in the UK was included

Arrange	Schedule follow-up contact, either in person or via telephone.	Book followup phone call for 4-8 weeks	A link to the WSAVA tooth brushing guide was included in the post-consultation email Interval to be agreed with the caregiver and clinician
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154 A consult template was created based on the modified 5As model. The consult template
155 allowed for consistency between clinicians and acted as a reminder to ensure all steps were
156 fulfilled.

157 Prior to discussing the modified 5As with the caregiver, a clinical assessment was made of the
158 patient. The clinical assessment was designed to identify appropriate HOH methods for each
159 patient. Presence of mouth pain and the patients temperament were assessed to ensure advice
160 given was clinically appropriate.

161

162 **Recruitment Phase**

163 In the Recruitment Stage, caregivers attending the Dick Vet General Practice (DVGP) were
164 verbally invited to the study and asked for consent to receive an email invitation. Any caregiver
165 attending in the period from March 2024-September 2024 for any cat or dog vaccination
166 appointment were eligible for invite, which amounted to approximately 530 caregivers based
167 on average vaccination consult frequency. Within the next week, consenting caregivers
168 received an email with a link to our Recruitment Survey, which collected data on their
169 demographics, their pet's details, and their current understanding and perceptions of their
170 pet's dental health (see Survey Design below). Weekly, these responses were collated by JM
171 who forwarded contact details only to DVGP staff to arrange the Initial Consult with the
172 caregiver. We aimed to recruit 50 caregivers to the survey, which would represent
173 approximately 10% of caregivers seen in that period.

174

175 **Dental Clinic Initial Consult**

176 The Initial Consult involved an appointment to the Dental Clinic, where a clinical exam was
177 conducted, a clinically relevant history taken, and then a clinical assessment of which Home
178 Oral Hygiene methods were acceptable in this patient. The consult template (see
179 supplementary information) was followed during each consultation and all consults were run by
180 LEW, a general practice veterinarian, or CH, a veterinary nurse (VTS dentistry). The 5As were
181 followed with the caregiver being **asked** which Home Oral Hygiene Methods were being used
182 daily, **advised** on personalised advise with examples tailored to the patient and lifestyle, **assess**
183 whether the caregiver was willing to start or adapt their Home Oral Hygiene approach, **assisting**
184 the caregiver on agreeing a plan with a demonstration, discussion the potential challenges with
185 solutions, and giving the caregiver supplementary materials highlighting information relevant to
186 the caregivers personal circumstances, and finally a follow-up call was booked for 4-8 weeks to
187 **arrange** a further check. A follow up phone appointment was booked at the end of each
188 consultation with confirmation sent via email along with a consultation summary as per the
189 template guidelines.

190

191 **End of Clinic Phase**

192 The follow-up call followed a similar format, with caregivers being consulted on what changes
193 they had made, and then a further follow-up arranged if the 5A protocol suggested it would be

194 useful. When caregiver and practitioner had achieved a mutual end, a follow-up email was sent
195 including a summary of the plans made and a link to the End of Clinic Survey.

196

197 **Retention Phase**

198 Six months after the caregivers last follow up call, a Retention Survey was sent via email. Up to
199 two reminder emails were sent after each of these surveys if there was no response within 2
200 weeks. If there was no further response, the caregiver was considered to have exited the study.

201

202 **Survey Design**

203 There were three surveys in this project, the Recruitment Survey, the End of Clinic Survey, and
204 the Retention Survey. The Recruitment Survey contained questions relating to the caregiver
205 and pet demographics, and assigned a unique identifier which the caregiver would be able to
206 use to respond to the following two surveys. It asked questions about the pet's dental health
207 and history, and the caregiver's hopes regarding dental health. The End of Clinic Survey asked
208 about the caregiver's experiences in the clinic, their satisfaction, and a series of questions
209 aimed at checking whether the 5As protocol was followed in the consult. Finally the Retention
210 Survey asked caregivers about their perceptions of their pets' overall dental health and any
211 changes since the start of the project, and whether caregivers felt they had achieved their
212 goals. The Recruitment and the End of Clinic Survey contained a knowledge question asking
213 participants to rank six HOH methods in order of effectiveness (Dental supplements to food or

214 water, dental chews, diets tailored specifically for dental health, gel or paste added as a
215 supplement, mechanical brushing (with brush or silicone tool) alone, mechanical brushing (with
216 brush or silicone tool) with a gel or paste). And all three surveys contained a behavioural
217 frequency question, asking caregivers how frequently they performed the six HOH methods on
218 a scale from: I never use this, less often than weekly, at least weekly, at least five times a week,
219 at least once a day.

220 The surveys were piloted with 10 friends, family and colleagues and minor changes to question
221 wording were made.

222

223 **Scoring Home Oral Hygiene Methods**

224 As HOH methods can be varied in mechanism, active ingredient, and frequency, we devised a
225 scoring system to indicate clinically relevant changes to HOH practice, based on recent
226 guidelines reviews (11,13) and reviewed by LEW and CH. For example, a caregiver may change
227 behaviour from rarely wiping their pet's teeth with a wipe to wiping their pet's teeth once a
228 week, but while this is an increase in frequency, it is not clinically relevant and would not
229 positively impact dental health. Therefore, the scoring system considers mechanism, active
230 ingredient, and frequency, to provide each caregiver-animal pair with a HOH score. A decrease
231 in score reflects positive clinically relevant changes to HOH behaviours, whereas an increase in
232 score reflects negative clinically relevant changes. The scoring system was available for

233 reference by the clinician and caregiver during the in-person consultation and is detailed in
234 Table 2.

235

236 **Table 2:** Home Oral Hygiene Methods Scoring System

SCORE	HOME ORAL HYGIENE GRADING SCALE
1	Brushing at least once a day AND food AND/OR chews at least once a day (+/- gels/sprays, food/water additive)
2	Brushing at least once a day AND gel/sprays AND/OR food/water additive at least once a day
3	Brushing at least once a day
4	Food AND/OR Chews at least once a day AND gel/sprays AND/OR food/water additive at least once a day
5	Food at least once a day (+/- Chews)
6	Gel/sprays at least once a day AND food/water additive at least once a day
7	Gel/sprays at least once a day OR Chews at least once a day
8	Food/water additive at least once a day
9	Nothing (or any of above fewer than once a day)

237

238 **Qualitative Clinic Reflection**

239 We were also interested in the experience of the practitioners following the clinic's conclusion.

240 A researcher previously unattached to the project (KH) was brought on to run semi-structured
241 interviews with LEW and CH. These ran in February 2025 after the dental clinic had concluded.

242 The interview schedule is available in the data repository. Interviews were run via Microsoft

243 Teams and transcribed by that program. KH checked transcriptions for legibility.

244

245 **Data Analysis**

246 To address H¹ (Caregiver knowledge regarding Home Oral Hygiene method effectiveness would
247 not change following the dental clinic) we asked caregivers in the Recruitment and End of Clinic
248 phase to rank six methods of Home Oral Hygiene in terms of what they considered most
249 effective. We used 'Score Voting' (41) to rank the six methods where non-scores were
250 considered as being non-preferred. This approach is similar to committee rankings of grant
251 proposals (41) and allows for a stated ranking as opposed to summing only the medians. We
252 then characterized difference in knowledge across the Recruitment and End of Clinic time
253 points.

254 To address H¹ (The caregiver self-reported frequency of effective Home Oral Hygiene
255 behaviours would not change following the dental clinic), we used Welch's ANOVA to compare
256 between time points (42).

257 To address H³, we scored each caregiver's HOH as described, and then explored differences in
258 HOH score between Retention and Post Consult stage (n = 21) via Student's T-Test, and across
259 all three stages (n = 13) via ANOVA.

260 All statistical analysis were performed in R (43), and utilised the tidyverse (44), likert (45), vote
261 (41), patchwork (46), nord (47), and ggstatsplot (48) packages.

262 We also utilised reflexive thematic analysis to explore the two semi-structured interviews. JM
263 conducted the analysis and it was sense-checked by KH. Reflexive thematic analysis was
264 considered appropriate for this approach due to its inbuilt acknowledgement of the need for

265 reflexivity, understanding the context of the researcher, and the perspectives brought by the
266 person analysing the data (49,50), and due to its flexibility in being able to be utilised for
267 smaller qualitative datasets such as this one (51,52).

268 **Results**

269 **Participants and Retention**

270 In total, 105 caregivers gave consent to be contacted. Of these, 61 (58%) responded to the
271 Recruitment Survey. One caregiver responded for two dogs. While caregivers were encouraged
272 to attend the clinic with as many animals as they wanted, they were asked to answer the
273 research survey regarding only one animal. This caregiver only responded to the Recruitment
274 Survey, so we arbitrarily selected the first animal they provided data about and disregarded the
275 second, resulting in 61 caregiver-animal pairs. Of the 61 pairs, 39 had an in-person appointment
276 at the clinic (64%). There were 22 caregiver-animals pairs who responded to the Recruitment
277 Survey but did not receive an appointment. For 4 (18%), the available times were not suitable,
278 and for 3 (14%) the trial ran out of appointment times before they were able to attend. For the
279 remaining 15 (68%) we were unable to collect data on why they did not attend the clinic.

280

281 21 (36%) responded to the End of Clinic Survey and 15 (24%) responded to the Retention
282 survey. Retention in clinical trials is a common challenge (53), and while there are few meta-
283 analyses of retention in veterinary trials, in paediatric trials, retention can run from 68%-92%
284 (54), so 24% can be considered low, and potential reasons for this are discussed below. Due to
285 a member of staff being on parental leave, there was a change to how participants were
286 reminded of the Retention Survey, resulting in some participants responding to the Retention

287 Survey without responding to the End of clinic Survey, meaning there are only 13 participants
288 (21%) who were followed throughout the project.

289

290 **Participants**

291 Caregivers were generally the principle caretaker or joint principle caretaker of their pet and
292 spent a large proportion of time with their pet. 87% of respondents brought a dog to the clinic,
293 and 13% brought a cat (Table 3).

294

295

296 **Table 3:** Caregiver and pet demographic data for 61 respondents

Question	Responses	n	Percentage
Pet Type	A dog	53	87%
	A cat	8	13%
Pet Sex	Male	31	51%
	Female	30	49%
Castration Status	Neutered (castrated)	25	41%
	Not neutered/intact	6	10%
	NA (e.g. female)	30	49%
Spay Status	Neutered (spayed)	25	41%
	Not neutered/still has seasons	5	8%
	NA (e.g. male)	31	51%
Pets Primary Caretaker	I am my pet's primary caretaker	39	64%
	It is an even split between me and other household members/other households	22	36%
Pets Living Situation	Mostly/always in the house	52	85%
	Mostly/always in the house but can access a garden without needing a door opened for them (e.g. has a doggy door)	8	13%
	Mostly/always outside the house or in a garden/kennel	1	2%
Feeding Responsibility	Mostly / always me	36	59%
	Evenly split between me and other members of my household	24	39%
	Mostly / always other members of my household	1	2%
Dental History	Yes, my pet has had some teeth removed by a veterinary professional	10	16%
	No, as far as I am aware, my pet has all their teeth.	50	82%
	Yes, my pet has some teeth missing, but I do not know the cause (e.g. they were missing before you adopted/obtained your pet)	1	2%

Question	Responses	n	Percentage
Has your pet ever had teeth removed?	Not sure	9	15%
	No	27	44%
	Yes	25	41%
How many hours did you spend with your pet in the average day last week?	mean	14.14	
	median	12.50	
	min	4.00	
	max	24.0	

297

298 The majority of animals (82%) had all of their teeth, so far as owners were aware, and 63% of
 299 caregivers reported that their pet occasionally or more often had an unpleasant breath odour.
 300 While most (70%) caregivers felt they had a little or good knowledge regarding dental health,
 301 79% of caregivers wanted to be managing their pet's dental health differently (Figure 1).

302

Figure 1: Current dog dental symptoms, history, and caregiver happiness with dental health and knowledge (n = 61)

304 **Changes to Knowledge**

305 In the Recruitment phase, in Condorcet voting run off, Mechanical Brush with a Paste or Gel
306 and Mechanical brushing were rated 6 (Most Effective) and 5 respectively, with Gel or Paste
307 alone and Supplements being considered a 2 and 1 (Least Effective). This suggests that pre-
308 clinic, knowledge was generally good, at least in terms of identifying brushing as the most
309 effective solution. In the Post Consult period, Mechanical Brush with Paste or Gel remained the
310 most effective solution, per Condorcet voting run off, but Chews overtook the Mechanical
311 Brush (Figure 2)

Figure 2: Results of Condorcet Voting Run-Off when caregivers were asked to rank the effectiveness of Home Oral Hygiene Practices at Recruitment (n = 61) and Post Consult (n = 22)

312

313 Changes to Behaviour

314 Participants were asked how frequently they conducted each HOH method at all three survey
 315 points, and while the Retention behaviours were not significantly different from Recruitment
 316 Behaviours, Chews were provided more frequently ($F_{\text{Welch}}(2,33.95) = 4.13, \omega^2_p = 0.14$ CI_{95%}
 317 [0.00, 1.00], $p = .02$) at both End of Clinic and Retention than they were at Recruitment, and

318 Mechanical Brush and Paste was performed more frequently at End of Clinic in comparison to
319 Retention ($F_{\text{Welch}}(2,27.53) = 10.51, \omega^2_p = 0.39$ CI_{95%} [0.13, 1.00], $p < .001$), but these
320 behaviours were only significant between Recruitment and End of Clinic, not between
321 Recruitment and Retention ($p_{\text{Holm-adj.}} < .001$).

322

Figure 3: Differences between Home Oral Hygiene behaviour frequencies between Recruitment, End of Clinic, and Retention surveys compared by Welch's ANOVA

324 **Changes to Home Oral Hygiene Score**

325 Across all three survey points, the Recruitment Survey had the highest HOH score (i.e. least
326 clinically effective management), and the End of Clinic phase had the lowest (i.e.. most clinically
327 effective management). Looking at only the 21 participants who engaged with the clinic and
328 responded to the End of Clinic survey, we see a significant improvement in clinically relevant
329 HOH practice (Figure 4), with average score decreasing from 6.48 to 3.86, a moderate effect
330 size ($t_{\text{student}} = 2.77, p = .01, g_{\text{Hedges}} = 0.58, 95\% \text{ CI}[0.13, 1.02]$).

Figure 4: Difference in Home Oral Hygiene Score (lower scores correspond to more clinically effective management) across 21 active participants between the Recruitment Phase and End of Clinic Phase

331 However, this difference did not remain significant when looking at the 13 participants who
 332 were followed throughout the study (Figure 5). HOH score did show improvement across the
 333 time points, but with only 13 participants, the study was not sufficiently powered to
 334 demonstrate a significant effect ($F_{\text{Fisher}}(1.64, 19.63) = 3.28, p = .07, \omega^2_p = 0.08, 95\%CI[0.00,$
 335 $1.00]$).

Figure 5: Difference in Home Oral Hygiene Score (lower scores correspond to more clinically effective management) across 13 caregivers followed throughout Dental Clinic Intervention

336 Evaluation of Clinic

337 In the End of Clinic survey, 86% of caregivers were satisfied or very satisfied with the consult
338 experience, however 14% (n=3) reported being very dissatisfied. One of these participants was
339 already maintaining good HOH practice, and upon reviewing clinical notes, it is possible their
340 advice was not clearly personalized for them. Another participant had expressed frustration
341 regarding perceived ineffectiveness and difficulty of brushing, and the third participant had
342 achieved their main goal of reducing halitosis despite reporting dissatisfaction. All participants
343 agreed that the consult discussed their current practice, and the clinician gave them a
344 recommendation.

345 In the Retention period, 40% of caregivers did not feel they had achieved their goal (one of
346 whom could not remember their goal), and 47% felt their pet's dental health had not improved
347 following the clinic (one caregiver felt their pet's health had gotten worse). 33% of caregivers
348 wanted to be doing something differently to manage their pet's health, mainly being able to
349 brush the teeth more consistently (n = 4) with one caregiver wanting to try options other than
350 supplements. The majority of caregivers (79%) were using products from the approved list
351 given after the first appointment. The route between goal achievement, happiness with pet's
352 dental health, and pet's dental health was not clear. When comparing the Retention responses
353 with the clinical notes, 5 (33%) participants who expressed some unhappiness or desire to be
354 doing better had actually achieved everything they were advised to do in the consult,
355 suggesting that there was a misalignment between the owner's expectations and clinician's
356 assessment.

357

358 **Thematic Analysis on Practitioner Perspective**

359 The structure, content, and importantly 'space' of the 5A consult offers the clinician an
360 approach to contextualised care that is often lacking in normal General Practice. The veterinary
361 consult is often a point of mismatched expectations between caregiver and veterinarian (55),
362 and veterinarians can utilise defensive consult strategies after bad experiences (56). While
363 both practitioners reported that having a template to follow sometimes felt clunky, the form of
364 the 5A structure itself was seen to have benefits, particularly where follow-up was integrated
365 so the consult remained a conversation with the client.

366 *"I thought that the follow up would be really helpful in engaging owners because often*
367 *you give them advice about, oh, your pet could do with a dental treatment or we*
368 *recommend that you start using this and then you don't see them again for several*
369 *months. So actually the telephone check in I felt was quite useful." - CH*

370 One aspect of the clinic that surprised the practitioners was the utility of dedicated space, and
371 the transformative nature that had on the consult. As diagnosis of a condition was not a
372 component of the consult, the clinic offered a highly valuable, unique time and space for
373 conversing with the caregiver. This has been observed in 'new puppy' consults, which are more
374 preventative, and is rarer in the adult animal space, where caregivers often feel their needs are
375 not met (55).

376 *"I just had during the dental clinics, I had more time and it was focused on that subject.*
377 *So it was actually really nice being able to chat to owners" - CH*

378

379 Finally, the enforcement of the conversational aspect of the consult coupled with the removal
380 of the diagnostic issue promoted an approach to contextualised care that the practitioners
381 found extremely helpful.

382 *“The clinical plan that I need is already set out is the same for every patient. It's just*
383 *about the contextualising it.” - LEW*

384

385

386 Discussion

387 In this study, we applied a clinician-developed, human behaviour change consult model in a
388 veterinary dental clinic to explore whether it would result in long-term behavioural changes in
389 HOH management. To our knowledge, this is the first instance of the 5A Model being adapted
390 for use in the veterinary context, and one of a limited number of studies exploring how human
391 behavioural change theories can support companion animal welfare. We showed that a Dental
392 Clinic based on the 5As model creates short-term increases in the frequency of HOH behaviours
393 such as mechanically brushing the teeth (H2), and short-term improvements in overall HOH
394 practice (H3), but we were unable to demonstrate conclusive maintenance of these behaviours
395 in a 6 month retention period, perhaps due to the large drop out rate from the study.

396

397 A modified 5As model could be used in GP veterinary practice by MRCVS and RVN to elicit
398 caregiver behaviour change to improve preventative healthcare for pets. More research is
399 needed to confirm the effectiveness of this modified model. This study supports the
400 development of future studies to explore the use of human behaviour change in healthcare
401 models in the GP veterinary setting.

402

403 Caregiver HOH Knowledge

404 An unexpected finding was the reversal in HOH effectiveness rankings following the clinic, with
405 22 participants putting Chews above Mechanical Brushing in the End of Clinic survey in

406 Condorcet Runn Off voting. While we recognise that knowledge alone cannot promote
407 behaviour change, accurate knowledge is still an important cornerstone of any behavioural
408 change (57,58). Therefore it is important to improve our understanding of this finding.

409 We have considered possible hypotheses for this finding. There are generally three possible
410 reasons why a finding might be wrong (50), that it reflects underlying bias in the data, that
411 finding is picking up a confounding effect, and that the finding reflects a lack of sampling power.
412 We discuss the self-selection limitation of the study below, but arguably these caregivers are
413 motivated to engage and attend the clinic, and arguably should be more likely to have a solid
414 knowledge base. Similarly, we address the low power within the study below, but Condorcet
415 Run-Off voting does not require a statistical threshold of significance, instead it is a
416 mathematical representation of a group's ranked preference (41). This leaves us with the
417 possibility that the finding is 'true' in that it reflects what the participants told us, but it is
418 picking an underlying confounding effect. When reviewing the raw data, the individuals who
419 gave chews a higher rank in the End of Clinic survey were ones who had been advised chews
420 and were consequently using them. Therefore, this finding may represent a recalibration of
421 perceived knowledge to avoid cognitive dissonance and guilt for not brushing. Additionally, it
422 may reflect a misunderstanding in the emphasis of the veterinary advice, in that caregivers
423 have 'got the wrong end of the stick'

424 However, we think this finding might represent an interesting development in recent
425 discussions regarding the tension between 'gold standard care' and 'contextualised care' (59).
426 'Gold Standard Care' carries with it an express statement that there is only one correct way to
427 do something, which does not marry well with the aforementioned complex and endlessly

428 unique forms of the caregiver-companion animal bond. Instead, 'contextualised care' aims to
429 integrate the range of appropriate treatments available with recognition of the individual
430 circumstances of the caregiver and patient (60). In this case, when we asked participants to
431 rank the effectiveness of HOH methods, and thus within context, the caregivers may be fairly
432 assessing Chews as more useful. LEW and CH highlight that they would frequently use the
433 phrase within the clinics, "a chew every day is better than a toothbrush on the shelf". We think
434 it's important to clearly state that contextualised care is not about accepting ineffective
435 therapies (61), but if we are arguing that 'gold standard' (brushing) is not appropriate in the
436 context of that patient(62), we must accept that chews may represent a valid, contextualised
437 and effective choice. Therefore, caregivers may recognise the efficacy because of their
438 accessibility and ease. This represents an area within the contextualised care that requires a
439 great deal more in-depth qualitative exploration to understand how effective care manifests for
440 caregivers.

441

442

443 **Supporting Behaviour Change in Companion Animal Caregivers**

444 The caregiver-vet relationship is similar but not directly comparable to the patient-doctor
445 relationship, as the caregiver and decision maker is not the patient themselves. Instead there is
446 a triad of care between veterinarian, caregiver, and animal, this has similarities to paediatric
447 models, which require specialized child orientated and patient orientated communication
448 (63,64). Paediatric management plans are advised to include the child where possible (65), but

449 how do we do this effectively with pets? The 'empowerment model' of the veterinary-caregiver
450 relationship promotes the veterinarian as both a knowledgeable expert, but also a counsellor
451 who supports caregivers to make decisions, but recognises there needs to be critical review in
452 light of the caregiver's understanding of their specific context (66). In this study, we found the
453 5As model supported caregivers to make short-term changes to HOH behaviours that, per
454 dental management guidance (13), would protect and support animal dental health. While we
455 were not able to demonstrate a longer term retention effect, this is a promising approach to
456 providing preventative healthcare in veterinary settings. Individual practices could set up these
457 forms of clinics with a 5As approach to tackle a range of issues. This supports the expert-
458 generated recommendations on how preventative healthcare fits into veterinary practice,
459 including particularly supporting conversations between practitioner and caregiver (67).

460 Furthermore, these 'diagnosis-free' consultations can be supported by veterinary nurses and
461 receptionists in their respective roles, supporting conversations and arranging follow-ups,
462 reflecting the inter-professional practice in veterinary settings (68).

463 Future research should focus on exploring other consult models, including possibly geriatric
464 care models and reduced-capacity models which reflect similar triads of care (69). Gathering
465 more data regarding how behaviour change operates in veterinary contexts, similar to work
466 happening in production contexts (25), is also important. Furthermore, robust qualitative
467 research into the less tangible elements of this approach, can help characterise the underlying
468 phenomena driving caregiver decision making.

469

470

471 **Limitations**

472 One of the foremost limitations of this work was the low retention rate resulting in a small
473 sample size.

474 We hoped to recruit 10% of caregivers seen in the recruitment period, and achieved this,
475 however the retention throughout the study phases was disappointing. As part of our
476 institution's ethical review, we are encouraged to limit the number of times participant
477 personal data is held, which led us to ask caregivers to create their ID label. However, it is highly
478 likely that had we elected to retain participant email addresses, the ability to personalise survey
479 invites and track responses would have resulted in greater retention.

480 We could have increased our response numbers by increasing our initial sample pool, but this
481 was deemed counterproductive. It was not possible to invite all registered caregivers via email
482 due to GDPR legislation. We elected to recruit at vaccination to support a representative
483 demographic of patients and caregivers. If we invited all caregivers who attended at any time,
484 our sampling would have been skewed towards older and more unwell patients who visit the
485 hospital more frequently. But in recruiting at vaccination we were recruiting for caregivers
486 already participating in preventative care. Anecdotally, the majority of caregivers presenting at
487 the Small Animal General Practice clinic are those who are very motivated to care for their
488 animals, and the vast majority of patients are vaccinated. There is always a challenge of
489 studying disengaged populations.

490 Overall, approximately 20% (n = 105) of caregivers seen in this period gave consent to be
491 contacted. While there was no means to record if a caregiver refused to be contacted, we
492 assume based on our response numbers that not all caregivers were asked. It is therefore
493 possible that there was an unintended selection criteria in that an animal with poor oral
494 hygiene or a caregiver asking about HOH may have acted as a reminder for the vet or
495 receptionist to ask for consent to be contacted regarding the study. In selecting caregivers
496 visiting for vaccination, we were selecting for caregivers who already demonstrated positive
497 behaviours in preventative healthcare.

498

499 **Conclusions**

500 In this study, we demonstrated that a human consult model aimed at promoting health-
501 conscious behaviours, the 5As model, has application in veterinary settings. Animal caregivers
502 can be supported in veterinary consultations to make positive welfare choices for their animals,
503 and this behaviour can be maintained, at least in the short term. Moreover, this model of
504 consult and approach to preventative healthcare supports contextualised care by engaging
505 caregivers in an empowering model style conversation with the veterinary practitioner, and has
506 the potential for improving animal health and welfare.

507

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510

511 **CRedit Statement**

512 LEW: Conceptualisation, Data curation, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration,

513 Resources, Validation, Writing original draft, Writing review and editing

514 FM: Conceptualisation, Resources, Data curation

515 CH: Resources, Data curation, Investigation, Project Administration; Writing review and editing

516 KH: Data curation, Validation, Formal Analysis

517 AC: Resources, Project administration

518 JRDM: Conceptualisation, Resources, Data Curation, Software, Formal Analysis, Validation,

519 Investigation, Visualisation, Methodology, Writing Original Draft, Project Administration,

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525 **Conflict of Interest**

526 The authors have no conflict of interest to declare

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